

A COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY OF FRUIT AND STEM BARK OF *CHIRABILVA* [*HOLOPTELIA INTEGRIFOLIA* (ROXB.) PLANCH] IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ECZEMA

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: *Chirabilva* [*Holoptelia integrifolia* (Roxb.) Planch] is one such medicinal plant that is described right from the time of *Charaka Samhita* and had a wide range of therapeutic effects. It is indicated in the treatment of *Vami*, *Pittaja Arsha*, *Krimi*, *Kushtha*, and *Prameha*. Eczema is broadly applied to a range of persistent skin conditions. These include itching, dryness, and something oozing out that are characterized by one or more of these symptoms: erythema, skin edema (swelling), scratches, and lichenification. **Methods:** A Clinical trial was carried out on 30 Patients of eczema aged 18 to 60 years with complaints of erythema, skin edema (swelling), scratches, and lichenification. They were equally divided into two groups i.e., *Chirabilva* fruit *Churna* (Group A) and *Chirabilva* Stem bark *Churna* (Group B) for 21 days locally applied on the affected part. The clinical assessment

was carried out before and after the treatment on basis of the EASI score. **Results:** The study shows that the overall effect of the treatment was found 69.15 % in Group A and 59.34% in Group B. The mean score of erythema, edema, scratches, and lichenification before treatment

was 2.71, 2.46, 2.88, 2.63 respectively which were reduced up to 0.92, 0.69, 0.66, and 0.1 after treatment with 65.78%, 71.87%, 76.92%, 62.06% relief respectively in group A, whereas it was 2.66, 2.66, 2.80, 2.90 respectively before treatment which was reduced up to 0.93, 1.13, 1.20, 1.20 relieved completely after treatment with 64.10%, 57.53%, 57.14%, 58.62% relief in group B. **Conclusion:** It was inferred that both *Chirabilva* fruit *Churna* and Stem bark *Churna* were effective and reduced the symptoms of Eczema. Both groups exhibited nearly the same effects.

KEYWORDS: Dermatitis, *Karanja*, *Putikaranja*, Skin diseases.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, the useful part of medicinal plants may be one or many, and different parts may be useful in different diseases or the same disease. So, evaluating the comparative efficacy of different parts of the same plant is very important. It can provide useful evidence for further investigations and therapeutic use. Clinical studies are essential for creating this evidence-based database to evaluate comparative efficacy.

The usable parts of *Chirbilva* [*Holoptelia integrifolia* (Roxb.) Planch] are fruits and stem bark as mentioned in API^[1] and other standard texts.^[2] An EMR project was done in the PG department of *Dravya Guna*,^{xx xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx} entitled “To evaluate the efficacy of *Holoptelia integrifolia* (locally known as *kanji*) and ground nut oil against eczema,” in which encouraging results were found. *Chirbilva* is indicated in the treatment of *Vami*, *Pitta Arsha*, *Krimi*, *Kushtha*, and *Pramehaas* per *Bhavprakash Nighantu*.^[3]

According to the National eczema association, one in 10 individuals will develop eczema during their lifetime, with prevalence peaking in early childhood.^[4] The incidence of skin disease is very high in Gujarat state. As per one report skin disease is ranked fifth in the top 15 causes of most years lived with disability, by sex, in 2016.^[5] The prevalence of atopic eczema in 56 countries had been found to vary between 3 and 20.5%.^[6]

Based on all the above facts *Chirabilva* fruit, as well as stem bark, was chosen for the evaluation of their comparative efficacy in Eczema.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection, Authentication, and Preparation of the Trial Drug

Botanically identified *Chirabilva* fruit and stem bark was collected from the periphery of Nadiad, Gujarat (Fig. 1.a and 1. b). It was authenticated by taxonomy expert, ^{xxx xxxxxx xxxxxx} ^{xxxxx} (Fig.1.c). A herbarium was prepared and submitted to the Dravyaguna Museum with a voucher specimen (specimen no. 242/2022) for future reference.

Plate 1.

Figure: 1.a

Figure: 1.b

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J. S. Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Nadiad (Guj.)
HERBARIUM SHEET

Serial No.: _____

Authenticated by

Dr. Gaurang Prajapati
 Principal
 J. & J. College of Science
 NADIAD.
 Signature of the Teacher

Name and Signature of the Student

Dr. Gaurang Prajapati

Basonym	Chirbilva
Classical names	चिरबिल्व
Regional name	સગમ
Botanical source	Holoptelea integrifolia
Family	Dilleniaceae
Classification according to	સગમ, સગમી, સગમી.
Approved	
Date of collection	29/02/22
Place of collection	Nadiad
Rasa	Tikta, Kashaya
Guna	Ushna, Madhura, Laghu
Veerya	Usna
Vipaka	Katu
Prabhava	
Major Chemical constituents	B-Sitosterol, Eriodolin
Active	Phenol
Major pharmacological actions	anti-inflammatory, analgesic
Parts Used	Bark (stem)
Important Formulations	Chirbilva-Usna, Chirbilva

Plate 2.

Figure: 2.a

Figure: 2.a

Figure: 2.b

Then collected root samples and stem bark samples were washed under running fresh tap water to remove adherent soil and dirt and then dried in shade for 28 days (Fig. 2.a and Fig. 2.b). The properly dried *Chirbilva* fruit and bark weighed equally 6 Kg. They were made into *Churna* (powder) and filtered through 120# mesh. The powder was preserved in separate airtight containers. These Powders were used to prepare Lepa (paste).

CTRI registration: The study was registered in the Clinical Trial Registry of India with no. CTRI/2021/03/031888 on 10/03/2021.

Selection of Patients: 30 Patients with eczema were enrolled from OPD of postgraduate departments of *Kayachikitsa* and *Panchakarma*,^{xx xxxxx xxxxxxx xxx}. Detailed history and complete general and systematic examination were done.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients between the age group of 18-60 years.
2. Patients having signs and symptoms of eczema.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with any other associated clinical condition.
2. Pregnant and lactating women.
3. Patients on steroid therapy.

Group Design

Patients were randomly divided into two groups by block random method^[7] in the clinical trial. Each group consisted of 15 patients and the groups were named groups A and B.

In group A, powder of *Chirabilva* fruit mixed with *Tila Taila* in a sufficient ratio to the affected part of the skin twice a day for 21 days while in group B, powder of *Chirabilva* stem bark mixed with *Tila Taila* in a sufficient ratio to the affected part of the skin twice a day for 21 days. All patients were advised to follow specifically prescribed *Ahara*, *Dincharya*, and *Rutucharya* as per classical Ayurvedic texts and instructed to avoid the causes of *Kustha Roga* as per texts.

Criteria for Assessment

All the patients were assessed before and after the treatment by using the following objective and subjective criteria.

Objective Criteria

1. Photo of the patch before and after the treatment.^[8]
2. Measurements of the area of patches.

Subjective criteria

Signs and symptoms were assessed as per the EASI score^[9] and performed before and after the treatment. (Table no. 1)

Table No. 1: Gradation as per EASI score.

WEEKLY SCORE	GRADE
0	Free
1-7.0	Well-controlled
7.1-21	Moderate
21.1-50	Severe
50.1-72	Very severe

Statistical Analysis

Results obtained were analysed statistically by the paired 't' test and unpaired 't' test.

RESULTS

The effect of *Chirbilva* fruit *Churna* on chief complaints in 15 patients of eczema has been depicted in table no. 2.

Table No. 2: Effect of *Chirbilva* fruit *Churna* on chief complaints in Group A.

Chief complaints	N	Mean score of BT	Mean score of AT	Diff. in mean score	Change in %	SD (\pm)	T	P value
Erythema	15	2.71	0.92	1.78	65.78	0.42	16.24	0.0060
Edema	14	2.46	0.69	1.76	71.87	0.59	11.04	0.0062
Scratches	10	2.88	0.66	2.22	76.92	0.83	8.43	0.049
Lichenification	12	2.63	1	1.63	62.06	0.50	11.23	0.0077

The mean score of erythema was 2.71 before the treatment and reduced by 0.92 after the treatment with 65.78% reduction. This beneficial effect was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of edema was 2.46 before the treatment and reduced by 0.69 after the treatment with 71.87% reduction. This beneficial effect was also found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of scratches was 2.88 before the treatment and reduced by 0.66 after the treatment with 76.92% reduction. The reduction in scratches was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of lichenification was 2.63 before the treatment and reduced by 01 after the treatment with 62.06% reduction. The reduction in lichenification was also found significant statistically ($p < 0.05$).

The effect of *Chirbilva* fruit *Churna* on associated complaints in 15 patients of eczema has been depicted in Table no. 3.

Table No. 3: Effect of *Chirbilva* fruit *churna* on associated complaints in Group A.

Associated Complaints	N	Mean score of BT	Mean score of AT	Diff. in mean score	Change in %	SD (\pm)	T	P value
Itching	15	2.85	0.57	2.28	80	0.46	18.83	0.0074
Dryness	05	1.8	0.2	1.6	88.88	0.54	6.53	0.019
Oozing	07	1.57	0.14	1.42	90.90	0.78	4.80	0.038

The mean score of itching was 2.85 before the treatment and reduced by 0.57 after the treatment with an 80% reduction. The reduction was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of dryness was 1.8 before the treatment and reduced by 0.20 after the treatment with an 88.88% reduction. This beneficial effect was also found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of oozing was 1.57 before the treatment and reduced by 0.14 after the treatment with 90.90% reduction. This beneficial effect was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The effect of *Chirbilva* stem bark *churna* on chief complaints in 15 patients of eczema has been depicted in table no. 4.

Table No. 4: Effect of *Chirbilva* bark *churna* on chief complaints in Group B.

Chief complaints	N	Mean score of BT	Mean score of AT	Diff in mean score	Change in %	SD (\pm)	T	P value
Erythema	15	2.66	0.93	1.66	64.10	0.72	8.91	0.010
Edema	15	2.66	1.13	1.53	57.53	0.74	7.99	0.015
Scratches	10	2.80	1.20	1.60	57.14	0.84	6	0.021
Lichenification	10	2.90	1.20	1.70	58.62	1.05	5.07	0.025

The mean score of erythema was 2.66 before the treatment and reduced by 0.93 after the treatment with 64.10% reduction. This beneficial effect was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of edema was 2.66 before the treatment and reduced by 1.13 after the treatment with 57.53% reduction. The reduction in edema was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of scratches was 2.80 before the treatment and reduced by 1.20 after the treatment with 57.14% reduction. This was also found significant statistically ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of lichenification was 2.90 before the treatment and reduced by 1.20 after the treatment with 58.62% reduction. The reduction in lichenification was also found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The effect of *Chirbilva* stem bark *churna* on associated complaints in 15 patients of eczema has been depicted in table no. 5.

Table No. 5: Effect of *Chirbilva* bark *churna* on associated complaints in Group B.

Associated Complaints	N	Mean score of BT	Mean score of AT	Diff. in mean score	Change in %	SD (±)	T	P value
Itching	15	2.6	0.46	2.13	82.05%	0.91	9.025	0.0049
Dryness	01	01	00	01	100%	-	-	-
Oozing	06	1.5	00	1.5	100%	0.54	5.71	0.026

The mean score of itching was 2.6 before the treatment and reduced by 0.46 after the treatment with an 82.05% reduction. This effect was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of dryness was 01 before the treatment which was relieved completely after the treatment with a 100% reduction. This beneficial effect was found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The mean score of oozing was 1.5 before the treatment and was also relieved completely after the treatment with a 100% reduction. It was also found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Comparative effect of therapy

Comparison between Group A and Group B in classical symptoms of Eczema has been depicted in table no. 6.

Table No. 6: Comparison between Group A and Group B in classical symptoms of Eczema.

Chief Complaints	Mean		Variance	Diff.	T value	P value
	Group A	Group B				
Erythema	1.8	1.66	0.34	28	0.619	0.540
Edema	1.78	1.53	-	26	1.023	0.315
Scratches	2.2	1.6	0.66	18	1.643	0.117
Lichenification	1.58	1.7	-	12	-0.31	0.775

When the results of Group A and Group B were compared, it was found that there is no significant difference between the results of Group A and Group B. But, the analysis by paired “t” test has shown better results in Group A.

Erythema was better relieved in group A based on a percentage of relief i.e., 65.78% than in group B i.e., 64.10%. This comparative data is not significant statistically ($p < 0.05$).

Group A showed better results on relief in edema i.e., 71.87% when compared with group B i.e., 57.53%. This comparative data is statistically not significant ($p < 0.05$).

In the same way, a better percentage of relief was found in group A in Scratches i.e., 76.92% as compared to group B i.e., 57.14%. This comparative data is also statistically not significant ($p < 0.05$).

In relieving Lichenification, group A showed a better result i.e., 62.06% than that of group B which is 58.62%. This comparative data is also statistically not significant ($p < 0.05$).

The overall effect of therapies

The overall effect of therapies in Group A and Group B is depicted in table no. 7.

Table No. 7: Effect of therapies in Group A and Group B.

Improvement	Group A (fruit)		Group B (bark)	
	No. of Pts.	Percentage	No. of Pts.	Percentage
Cured	05	33.33%	06	40%
Well control	10	66.66%	09	60%
Overall effect	69.15		59.34%	

In group A, 05 patients were cured and 10 patients were having good control over the signs and symptoms of eczema. The overall effect of the treatment in group A was 69.15 %.

In group B, 06 patients were cured and 09 patients were having good control over the signs and symptoms of eczema. The overall effect of the treatment in group B was 59.34%. so, group A is statistically significant compared to Group B.

DISCUSSION

The effect of *Chirabilva* can be explained based on *Rasapanchaka*. *Chirbilva* has *Tikta-kashaya Rasa*; *Tikshana*, *Ruksha*, *Sara Guna*; *Katu Vipaka*; *Usna Virya*, and *Vatavritta Kapha-Pitta hard*^[10] qualities which help to resolve *Samprapti*. Hence, *Chirabilva* can be used in the management of *Tridoshaja Vyadhi* like *Kushtha*. The signs and symptoms of eczema are like the clinical features of the disease condition *Kushtha* mentioned in Ayurveda. As per ancient books, *Kushtha* is *Tridoshaja Vyadhi*. *Chirabilva* is also having *Kushthaghna*^[11] action which is helpful to relieve signs and symptoms of *Kushtha*.

Erythema is caused by aggravated *Pitta Dosha*. *Chirabilva* has *Tikta-Kashaya rasa*, which reduces vitiated *Pitta Dosha* and provides relief in erythema. The vitiated *Kapha Dosha* is responsible for edema.^[12] *Chirabilva* possesses *Tikta-Kashaya Rasa* and *Tikshana*, *Ruksha*, and *Sara Guna*. By the virtue of these properties, it can pacify vitiated *Kapha Dosha* and

reduces edema. Scratches are caused by itching. *Vata-Kapha Hara* properties and *Kandughna* action of *Chirabilva* reduce itching and ultimately scratches are reduced. Lichenification in the skin is produced mainly by aggravated *Kapha Dosha*. *Chirabilva* possesses *Tikta-Kashaya Rasa*, *Tikshana*, *Ruksha*, *Sara Guna*, and *Katu Vipaka*. By the virtue of these properties and *Kushthaghna* action, it can pacify vitiated *Kapha* and reduce lichenification. And in *Ayurveda*, many references to *Lepana Karma*^[13] in *Kustha* and the virtue of *Rasapanchaka* are taken as a root of administration. There were many references observed of *Chirbilva* as an external application.^[14] Though it is used externally. Paste of the stem bark is externally applied to treat the inflammation of lymph glands, ringworm, and scabies. Decoction of the leaves is used to regulate fat metabolism and treat ringworm, eczema, and cutaneous diseases.^[15]

Action as per modern pharmacological activity

Modern research has proved that *Chirabilva* [*Holoptelia integrifolia* (Roxb.) Planch] has anti-inflammatory^[16], anthelmintic^[17], antioxidant^[18], Antifungal activity^[19], and Antibacterial activity.^[20]

The anti-inflammatory effect, kills the causative microorganism i.e., *Trichophyton*, *Microsporum*, and *Epidermophyton*, and reduces inflammation.^[21]

Holoptelia integrifolia has broad antifungal potential. The alcoholic stem extracts of *H. integrifolia* were studied for antifungal activity against five fungal strains, namely, *Candida Tropicana*, *Candida krusei*, *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* using the agar well diffusion method.^[22]

Chirbilva [*Holoptelia integrifolia* (Roxb.) Planch] has antibacterial effect of hexane, diethyl ether, acetone, and aqueous extracts of *Holoptelea integrifolia* (Roxb.) Planch against the lactam-resistant strain of *staphylococcus aureus*.^[23]

By this all activities *Chirbilva* [*Holoptelia integrifolia* (roxb.) Planch] is useful in eczema.

CONCLUSION

Chirabilva fruit *Churna* and Stem bark *Churna* were effective and reduced signs and symptoms of Eczema. Both groups exhibited nearly the same effects. Hence it can be concluded that there is no major difference between the outcomes of the management of eczema with *Chirabilva* fruit and stem bark. *Chirabilva* fruit can be used in place of

Chirabilva bark because the repeated collection of bark will harm the tree, so the fruit can be a good alternative source in the management of Eczema.

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